

Crop management

Effect of traditional and improved nursery methods on seedling growth and rice yield

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In the Konkan region of Maharashtra, rice seedlings traditionally are raised on a flat nursery bed on which a large quantity of cow dung, twigs of trees (*Terminalia* spp.), dry grass, and dry leaves of forest trees have been burned. To further increase soil temperature, burning is slowed by spreading a thin layer of fine soil on top of the organic matter.

Each year, branches of forest trees and bushes are cut to collect organic matter. That eventually depletes the forests and degrades the soils. In the summer, skeletons of *Terminalia* trees and burned patches of fields are common sights.

Weed control seems to be the only objective of this traditional method. Although the seedlings raised are vigorous, long-term detrimental effects do not warrant the short-term advantages.

We evaluated the traditional method against improved methods of raising seedlings in two consecutive experiments during 1988 wet season. Treatments included preburning of nursery bed and raised and flat nursery beds with various mechanical and herbicidal weed control treatments (see table).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil of the experimental plot was lateritic having 152.5, 6.9, and 248.9 kg available N, P, K/ha. Plot sizes were 6 × 1 m for the nursery and 4.6 × 4.2 m for transplanting. Nursery area burning was done in May 1988 and Ratnagiri 24 was planted in Jun 1988. Preemergence herbicides were applied on wet soil.

Seedlings from the set of nursery treatments were transplanted in a different field in a randomized block design with three replications. Recommended plant population (20 × 15 cm), fertilizers (100 kg N, 22 kg P/ha), and plant protection measures were applied uniformly to all treatments.

Seedling height and dry matter in the traditional rice nursery were more than twice that in the other nursery treatments (see table). This could be attributed to increased availability of N (10%), P (39%), and K (100%). Also, all weeds were eliminated.

However, the pretransplanting differences did not significantly affect crop yields. Seedlings from the traditional nursery were not superior to seedlings from improved nurseries.

Thus, the traditional method benefits only the nursery and should be discouraged to save valuable organic matter and vegetation. Instead, herbicides should be used to control weeds in the nursery. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Nonfluorescent *Pseudomonas* strains causing rice sterility and grain discoloration in Colombia

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Two nonfluorescent species of *Pseudomonas*, *P. avenae* and *P. glumae*, cause seedling rot, grain discoloration (GID), and sterility in rice. *P. avenae* is known to be distributed worldwide; until a recent report from Latin America, *P. glumae* was known only in Asia. Reports on the

Effect of preburning nursery bed and raised and flat bed nurseries with different weed control methods on seedling growth and transplanted rice yield.^a

Treatment	Seedling height (cm)	Dry matter/seedling (mg)	Dry weight of weeds (t/ha)	Weed control efficiency (%)	Available N (kg/ha)	Available P (kg/ha)	Exchangeable K (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Rabbing (preburning)	10.5	115.0	-	100	168.7	9.9	439.1	2.4	3.0
Raised bed + unweeded control	5.8	42.0	1.2	13.3	152.7	6.8	233.8	2.4	2.8
Raised bed + weed-free check	6.3	47.3	0.3	75.9	153.5	7.1	224.0	2.8	3.2
Flat bed + unweeded control	5.7	40.0	1.4	0.0	156.1	6.9	237.2	2.3	2.8
Flat bed + weed-free check	6.0	46.3	0.3	75.9	150.3	7.2	237.2	2.8	3.1
Raised bed + one hand weeding	5.8	49.3	0.3	76.3	153.1	7.0	240.5	2.8	3.0
Flat bed + one hand weeding	5.7	46.3	0.3	75.9	152.6	6.9	233.1	2.3	2.8
Raised bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 50 EC/ha at preemergence	5.3	34.6	0.2	85.1	146.1	7.0	238.7	2.2	2.6
Flat bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 50 EC/ha at preemergence	5.5	36.0	0.2	84.7	146.1	7.1	241.8	2.1	2.8
Raised bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 10% G/ha at preemergence	4.9	33.6	0.2	85.1	144.9	6.9	234.4	2.3	2.7
Flat bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 10% G/ha at preemergence	5.7	38.0	0.2	84.7	151.4	6.9	238.8	2.2	2.7
Raised bed + 1.0 kg ai oxadiazon/ha at preemergence	4.9	37.0	0.2	85.5	151.4	7.0	229.2	2.4	2.8
Flat bed + 1.0 kg ai oxadiazon/ha at preemergence	5.9	41.0	0.2	85.1	154.3	6.9	237.3	2.5	2.9
LSD (0.05)	1.1	9.9	0.1		6.5	0.6	25.4	ns	ns

^a Nursery variables measured at time of uprooting seedlings.

characteristics of these species differ. We undertook to more completely characterize strains reported as *P. glumae* found in Latin America. We also compared the characteristics of the two species to clarify some discrepancies in published descriptions.

Three strains of a nonfluorescent pathogenic bacterium obtained from discolored rice grains collected from farmers' fields in Colombia were compared with four culture collection strains of *P. glumae* and 25 strains of *P. avenae* (6 culture collection strains and 19 strains previously identified at CIAT), using standard bacteriological techniques. The culture collection strains included type specimens of each species.

The pathogenic strains recovered from discolored grains were consistent with *P. glumae*, rather than with *P. avenae* (see table). All strains tested could be distinguished from *Erwinia herbicola* in that they did not grow anaerobically and had multiple polar flagella. However, some differences were observed among the field-collected strains and the strains of known identity, as well as differences from published characteristics of the species.

The original description of *P. glumae* referred to it as producing a fluorescent pigment on potato agar. This probably referred to the diffusible green nonfluorescent pigment that we and others have observed to be produced by some, but not

all strains. The growth limit for *P. glumae* has been reported to be 40 °C; however, the strains in this study all grew at 41°C.

Researchers in the U.S., in establishing the synonymy of *P. alboprecipitans* and *P. setaria* with *P. avenae* (*P. menae* is now considered to be the correct name for this pathogen), described their strains as oxidase negative. More recently, researchers in Japan described their strains as oxidase positive. We have found our strains to be oxidase positive.

The Japanese researchers also reported that their strains grew in 3% NaCl but not in 5% NaCl. Our strains grew in 5% NaCl. The Japanese reported negative tobacco hypersensitivity, lipase, and H₂S production. Our strains were positive, negative, and variable, respectively. The strains we identified as *P. avenae* and *P. glumae* also abundantly accumulated poly-b-hydroxybutyrate crystals. ■

Phenotypic characteristics^a three *Pseudomonas* strains that cause grain discoloration and sterility in Colombian ricefields compared to strains of *P. glumae* and *P. avenae*.

Phenotypic character	<i>P. glumae</i> (4 strains)	Colombian strain			<i>P. avenae</i> (25 strains)
		1445-4-1	1445-4-2	1462-7-2	
Fluorescent pigment	-	-	-	-	-
Arginine dihydrolase	-	+	+	+	+
Nitrate reduction	-	-	-	-	+
Oxidase	-	-	-	-	+
Diffusible green pigment	d (50)	+	+	-	-
Accumulation of poly-b-hydroxybutyrate crystals	+	+	+	+	+
Utilization for growth					
Arabinose	+	+	+	+	d (60)
Cellobiose	+	+	+	+	-
Raffinose	+	+	+	+	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Xylose	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Adonitol	+	+	+	+	-
Inositol	+	+	+	+	-
Sorbitol	d (75)	-	-	-	+
Arginine	d (75)	+	+	+	-
Salicine	+	+	+	+	-
Acid from					
Dextrose	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Lactose	-	-	-	-	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Mannitol	+	+	+	+	d (76)
H ₂ S from TSI	-	-	-	-	d (76)
Catalase	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Gelatin liquefaction	d (50)	+	+	+	-
Growth at 41°C	+	+	+	+	+
Growth in 5% NaCl	+	+	+	+	+
Indole	-	-	-	-	-
Lecithinase	+	+	+	+	-
Levan from sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Lipase	-	-	-	-	-
Pit formation on CVP	-	-	-	-	-
Starch hydrolysis	-	-	-	-	+
Tobacco hypersensitivity	+	+	+	+	+
Pathogenicity on rice	+	+	+	+	+

^a + = 90% or more of strains positive, - = 90% or more of strains negative, d = 11-89% strains positive; number in parentheses is percent of strains positive.

False smut incidence on rice relative to plant characters and environmental factors

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We studied false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens* Tak. incidence on 32 rice cultivars and the relationship of disease severity to plant characters and ambient environmental factors in the 1987 dry season. Rice cultivars were dry seeded in upland conditions, in a completely randomized block design with three replications. False smut of panicles at maturity was recorded for each cultivar. Disease severity, infected panicles, and number of infected florets on the most infected panicle were recorded.

B3719C-TB-8-1-4, China 988, HPU2202, HPU5101, Nag 1-38, VL 501, and VRS1 were disease free. Disease severity on the 26 susceptible cultivars ranged from 1 to 17.9%. A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.54$) between plant height (range 70-135 cm) and disease severity indicated that short cultivars were more vulnerable than tall ones.

The correlation of disease severity and days to 50% flowering was not signifi-